

Background

Image theatre is an approach based on the Theatre of the Oppressed¹, and was originally designed to explore socio-political power dynamics. The image theatre scripts for Vital are designed to be used as a tool to explore the dynamics of power and agency in our relationships to food, including each other and non-humans.

The scripts should be used in sequence with a group of 4+, with discussions facilitated by the workshop leader. All Participant Actor parts should be interpreted non-verbally, so that acting is portrayed through body positions alone, and not through spoken language. This is more congruent with the variety of roles in the scripts, and brings to the fore the importance of embodied knowledge in social interactions and relationship building².

¹ [Image Theater, Beautiful Trouble: A Toolbox for Revolution](#), retrieved 2. February 2018

² [Intercorporeality as a theory of social cognition](#) (2015), S. Tanaka, *Theory & Psychology*, 25 (4), 455 - 472

Scene 1: Buying water

Roles

Participant Actor 1: customer

Participant Actor 2: retailer

Script

Act	Action
1. Customer goes into shop, retailer is in the shop	Interpretive discussion of body positions
2. Customer goes to buy water	Interpretive discussion of body positions. What does the positioning tell us about the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none">● What is important to each person in this transaction?
3. Walk beyond	Interpretive discussion of body positions. What does the positioning tell us about the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none">● How important is the social interaction?● How important is the water?● How does this reflect on the value of the water?

Scene 2: Swimming

Roles

Participant Actor 1: subject 1

Participant Actor 2: water

Participant Actor 3: water

Participant Actors 4: water

Script

Act	Action
1. Subject 1 enters water	Interpretive discussion of body positions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Where does the agency lie?
2. Subject 1 begins to swim	Interpretive discussion of body positions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Where does the agency lie?● Is all water the same?
3. Subject 1 decides to stop swimming and float in the water	Interpretive discussion of body positions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Has the way we interpret agency changed?

Scene 3: Walking in the rain

Roles

Participant Actor 1: subject 1

Participant Actor 2: subject 2

Participant Actor 3: rain

Participant Actor 4: tree

Script

Act	Action
1. Subjects 1 and 2 walk into the park	Interpretive discussion of body positions
2. Rain begins to fall	Interpretive discussion of body positions. What does the positioning tell us about the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The agency of the rain ● Emotional response to water ● Physical response to water ● Agency of rain on human relationships
3. Rain gets heavier	
4. Rain stops	
7. All depart	